

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004) № ISSUE 5 30.05.2024

ME'MORCHILIK VA QURILISH MUAMMOLARI

(ilmiy -texnik jurnal) 30.05.2024 № 5-son

ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА

(научно-технический журнал) 30.05.2024 № ВЫПУСК-5

Jurnal OAK Hay'atining qaroriga binoan texnika (qurilish, mexanika va mashinasozlik sohalari) fanlari hamda me'morchilik bo'yicha ilmiy maqolalar chop etilishi lozim bo'lgan ilmiy jurnallar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan (guvohnoma №00757. 2000.31.01)

Jurnalimizdagi ingliz tilida chop etilgan maqolalar OAK Rayosatining 2020 yil 30 iyuldagi 283/7.1-son qaroriga asosan xorijiy ilmiy nashrlarda chop etilgan ilmiy maqolalarga teng lashtirilganini ma'lum qiladi.

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ENSURING TRAFFIC SAFETY IN OPERATION OF TRANSPORT NETWORKS

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Abstract: This article discusses the features of the adhesion of the pavement of the street and road network, to a certain extent affecting the length of the path of deceleration or stopping of the car, its priority and controllability, as well as the smoothness of movement along the streets and the carriageway, methods of dividing the traffic flow into lanes by speed, the work performed on the organization of traffic, methods of work of projects to ensure and organize traffic safety in difficult road conditions.

Keywords: street and road networks, cross-country ability, coefficient of longitudinal adhesion, braking, the concept of “fluency”, capital coatings, special specialized lanes.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены особенности сцепления покрытий уличной и дорожной сети, в определенной степени влияющие на длину пути замедления или остановки автомобиля, его приоритет и управляемость, а также на плавность движения по улицам и проезжей части, методы разделения автомобильного потока на полосы по скоростям, выполняемые работы по организации движения, методы работы проектов по обеспечению и организации безопасности движения в тяжелых дорожных условиях.

Ключевые слова: уличные и дорожные сети, проходимость, коэффициент продольного сцепления, торможение, понятие “беглость”, капитальные покрытия, специальные специализированные полосы.

Adhesion properties of road and street surfaces determine to a certain extent the length of the car's deceleration or stopping path, have a great influence on its priority and control, therefore, it is an important parameter affecting traffic safety.

1. A smooth road surface has a high adhesion regardless of roughness in a dry and clean state. During the rainy season, the layer of water reduces the direct contact with the surface of the tire, which leads to a decrease in its grip properties. [1] [2]

The adhesion property of the coating depends on the roughness of its surface in the wet state. Smooth pavements that are dangerous for motor vehicle traffic cannot be distinguished by sight from relatively safe small bumps. Therefore, in order to identify

possible dangerous parts of the road, it is necessary to constantly evaluate the adhesion properties of the improved pavements built with binders in their wet state with special tools designed for this purpose.

2. As an indicator of the adhesion characteristics of road and highway pavements, the coefficient of longitudinal adhesion of a car tire to the road surface is taken, which occurs during the longitudinal sliding of the locked wheel and on the surface. It is expressed by the ratio of the longitudinal impact of the street and the road, which is affected at its connection with the pavement, to the normal impact of the network in the region of the connection. [3] [4]

3. Longitudinal adhesion coefficient is measured with dynamometric instruments

equipped with a special tire with a smooth coating of dimensions 6.45-13, internal air pressure of 0.17 MPa, at which the sliding speed of the locked wheel is 17 m/s ± The vertical weight acting on the wheel at 1 m/s is 2.943 kN ± 0.1 kN.

If the wheel of the measuring instrument does not have a special tire with a smooth coating (tread), it is allowed to use a worn tire with a depth of the grooves of the coating (tread) no more than 1 mm. To measure the performance coefficient, a standardized tool PKRS-2 (State Register Order No. 10913-87) or PPK-MAYI-VNIIBD (State Register Order No. 10912-87) is use. [4] [5]

4. When the coefficient of friction is measured, the individual system of artificial moistening installed on the vehicle-scooter of the dynamometric instrument is used to moisten the street and road surface. The artificial wetting system must ensure that enough water is transferred to the contact region of the sliding measuring wheel to form a layer of liquid (curtain) with a thickness of 1 mm ± 0.3 mm on the coating.

5. Depending on the traffic conditions, the minimum permissible values of the coefficients of engagement are as follows.

Traffic condition	light	difficult	Dangerous
Coefficient of mixing	0,28	0,30	0,32

6. If, as a result of the measurement, the adhesion coefficients are smaller than those specified in point 5, the roughness of the coating should be increased. When entering slippery parts of the road, it is required to install speed limit signs and a table indicating the need to reduce speed only when the road is wet. [5]

7. In practice, the braking distance and road length method is used to estimate the

braking coefficient. In this method, a vehicle equipped with a brake start indicator is used instead of a gear ratio measuring device. As a marker, a device that drops liquid or dry paint onto the surface of the pavement when the brake pedal is pressed is used. The essence of the method is to determine the length of the braking distance of a moving car from a certain speed to a complete stop. The size of the coupling coefficient is determined using the following formula:

$$\varphi = \frac{V}{254 \cdot S_T} \pm i$$

here, V is the speed at the start of braking in km/h; St is the length of the braking distance during the measurement, m; i is the longitudinal slope in the braking section, ‰.

Requirements for the smoothness of the street and road surface - the surface must be smooth to ensure safe and comfortable movement on the street and road. The unevenness of the street and road surfaces causes the car to vibrate, which causes the driver to tire quickly, slow down or increase the braking distance, and lead to poor control. In addition, the interaction of the car wheel with the unevenness of the road surface creates dynamic forces that cause rapid deterioration of the road surface.

1. The concept of "smoothness" refers to the geometric characteristics of the surface of the pavement, it is determined by the size and shape of the real surface of the street and road. [3] [5] [6]

2. The metrics used to assess fluency depend on the type of measuring instrument used and its performance basis.

In the CIS countries, various types of 3-meter level gauge (vibration meter) and the PKRS-2 device are used to assess the smoothness of road surfaces. Measurement

methods for each of the mentioned devices are presented in the manuals attached to them. 3-meter reticle readings are accepted as the basis, provided that readings of other types of instruments are provided using existing comparative links.

3. Ravonlikni baholashda 3 metrli reyklar bilan o'lchash yuqori ish hajmiga egaligi

sababli ular onda-sonda qo'llaniladi va asosan uncha katta bo'lmagan masofadagi ko'cha va yo'l qismlarida oralatib tekshirishlarda qo'llaniladi.

3-metrli reyka bilan o'lchanganda ko'cha va yo'l qoplamasining ravonligining ko'rsatkichlari 1- jadvalda keltirilgan qiymatlardan oshmasligi kerak.

Table 1

Coating type and measurement sizes	Fluency assessment		
	excellent	good	Satisfactory
Capital coatings number of cracks, %; up to 3mm	95	90	80
More than 5mm	1	2	5
The largest fixed crack, mm	7	8	10
Lightweight coatings up to 3mm	95	90	80
More than 7mm	1	2	5
The largest fixed crack, mm	9	11	14
Permeable coatings % of cracks: up to 8 mm	95	90	80
More than 15mm	1	2	5
The largest fixed crack, mm	20	25	30

During road use, the number of the largest cracks listed in Table 1 should not exceed the values listed in, Table 2.

4. A vibration meter or PKRS-2 device is used to assess the flow over a long distance. In this case, the fluidity is estimated according

to the total compression of the car spring and is expressed in smgkm. The maximum allowable indicators of flow when measured by TXK tolchkamer (vibration meter) are given in table 3 in cm/km.

Table 2

Coating type	The maximum number of cracks under the 3-meter rail for the following road levels,%		
	I, II	III, IV	IV, V
Capital (10 mm)	6-7	7-12	12
Lightweight (14mm)	-	7-10	10
Transient (30 mm)	-	-	5

Table 3

Grade	Pavement smoothness indicators measured with a vibration meter for the following pavements		
	capital	eased	passing
Excellent	60(70)	80(90)	200(300)
Good	61-80(71-100)	81-120(91-140)	201-280(231-320)
satisfactory	81-120(101-140)	121-180(141-210)	281-400(321-460)

5. Fluency indicators measured on the PKRS-2 device have the following permissible limit values:

Table 4

Grade	excellent	good	satisfactory
Fluency indicators, cm/km	390	341-480	481-650

There are two main ways of organizing traffic, which are to divide the flow of vehicles into speed bands and routes. [7]

When dividing the traffic flow into speed bands, the following actions are performed:

1. On multi-lane streets and roads, specially specialized lanes are provided for slow-moving cars, buses, trolleybuses, local vehicles, transit vehicles and bicycle traffic.

2. An additional strip for slow-moving vehicles will be built on steep sections of the street and road.

3. Lanes are made for braking and acceleration at complex intersections.

4. In front of the street and road facilities that provide services for vehicles, pedestrians and passengers, there are lanes and areas for standing and stopping.

5. "Pockets" are built for stopping buses along with braking and acceleration strips at public transport stops.

The following activities are planned for the separation of the flow of cars by directions:

1. Placement of the street and road traffic section in separate directions on a single road base with the help of a separating strip, for example, on the section of the Tashkent-Bukhara highway to Jizzakh, THAI, Moscow-Domodedova and others.

2. Placing the carriageway on separate roads, for example, on the Tashkent-Shymkent road and on most foreign roads.

3. Installation of safety islands that separate directions in curves with a small radius that does not provide visibility (on the curved sections of the Tashkent-Dushanba

highway up to Syrdarya, on the Tashkent-Ko'kan, Kushka-Khirot highways).

4. Organization of one-way traffic on parallel streets in residential areas.

5. Placement of traffic roads intersecting at intersections at different levels.

6. Separation of waiting lanes with the help of safety islands (through road marking lines) for left-turning cars to wait at level crossings.

Regardless of which method is used to organize traffic, it is necessary to use road signs, road marking lines, road barriers and automatic control equipment. By using the specified methods and technical means, it is possible to increase the speed of movement, capacity and ensure safety as a result of organizing traffic on this or that road section. [5] [7]

The work performed during the organization of the movement must meet the following requirements:

a) gradual change of traffic speed along road sections;

b) the direction of the front sections of the road should be clear and clear for the driver to move at any time of the day;

c) fast and safe movement of vehicles;

g) transfer of vehicles to the maximum extent;

d) to be environmentally friendly;

y) convenient and safe movement of pedestrians;

j) to be economically efficient.

Heavy road conditions include the following streets and road sections:

- intersections and road stops;

- curves with a small radius in the plan;

- places of steep ascent and descent;
- plots with no visibility;
- residential areas;
- Sections where car-tractor movement is observed;
- places with narrow bridges, overpasses, overpasses.

In such difficult road conditions, movement is organized based on the following principles:

1. Installation of road signs, street and road marking lines, street and road barriers and guiding devices based on the road conditions and the mode of movement of vehicles.

2. Change planning.

3. Transition to automated control (installation of traffic light objects controlled by a green wave, coordination of control, etc.).

4. Reducing the amount of traffic in some areas during peak hours.

5. Organization of unilateral action.

6. Creating the optimal route of public and freight transport.

7. Improvement of drivers' visibility of the front sections of the street and road.

8. Designation of additional tape.

9. Prohibiting the passage of certain vehicles.

10. Dividing vehicles into lanes based on their speed.

11. Division of vehicles according to their directions.

12. Construction of braking and acceleration bands.

13. Designation of the pedestrian crossing on the ground, underground and over the road.

14. Construction of security islands.

15. Construction of sidewalks for pedestrians.

16. Traffic management according to the variable scheme.

When driving on the road, there is a conflict between the desire of the driver to reach the destination faster and its implementation. In most cases, traffic safety is not ensured because the speed chosen by drivers does not take into account road, weather conditions and traffic flow characteristics. Such a situation creates conflicting conditions on the streets and roads.

One way to solve this problem in the future is to organize traffic management on highways, which includes:

- collection and analysis of information on road conditions and traffic flow;

- choosing the optimal mode of action in each specific case;

- providing operational information to the participants of the movement about the recommended mode of movement and monitoring its implementation.

It is necessary to ensure maximum traffic safety at intersections and junctions of automobile roads and roads. This depends on their location at a favorable angle to each other, the amount of traffic on intersecting or connecting roads, the visibility distance, constant parameters for controlling traffic on the highway by technical means, and periodically changing parameters (fluency, drivers regularly need information on gear ratio, amount of movement, load factor, etc.).

Currently, more technical means and new methods are used to manage traffic on the streets and highways. This includes an automatic traffic control system. with the help of the automatic traffic management system, it will be possible to choose economically favorable traffic management routes, taking into account the road conditions and the state of the traffic flow.

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